

MAIN FEATURES OF PHYSICAL TRAINING

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Abstract: The article discusses the main features of physical culture and training in human's life. Some specific sides have been counted in the work. There can be seen some special issues in developing physical culture lessons in Uzbekistan.

Key words: physical culture, people's health, physical fitness, mental abilities, moral purification, physical condition.

Physical culture is a part of general human culture, a sphere of social activity aimed at strengthening human health and developing physical abilities. The main indicators of the state of physical culture in society: people's health and physical fitness, the extent to which physical culture is implemented in the field of upbringing and education, in life, achievements in sports, etc. k. Physical culture includes folk games, physical exercises, sports and forms of tourism that require active movement. Physical culture was formed and developed in connection with such sciences as medicine, ecology, pedagogy, psychology. It has a direct impact on the development of society, people's effective work, the development of mental abilities, moral purification, and the physical condition of future generations. Physical education, physical education is an integral part of general education aimed at strengthening health and harmonious development of the human body. It is one of the indicators indicating the state of physical culture in society. The main means of physical education: physical training, physical training, work and life hygiene. Physical education, intellectual, moral, work and aesthetic education are carried out together. Special attention has been paid to physical education since the elementary period. Initially, it represented various rituals, which existed in the form of physical exercises, various games, labor processes, hunting, competitions and trials similar to military operations. Later, training young people in swordsmanship, horse riding,

archery, and one-on-one combat became one of the main tasks of the society. During the renaissance, attention to physical education became even stronger. Humanists tried to include physical education in the curriculum. In medieval Europe, physical education was considered as an important part of family education and pedagogical process in school. J. J. Rousseau emphasized the importance of physical education in children's mental maturity and work education in his pedagogical treatise called "Emile, or About Education". In the 18th century, mainly under the influence of Rousseau's ideas, the "schools of humanity and good behavior" - philanthropists, which appeared in Germany, led to the improvement of the forms and methods of physical education. Gymnastics takes a strong place in the school curriculum. At the end of the 19th century and the beginning of the 20th century, France, Great Britain, etc. National systems of physical education were formed in the countries. In Uzbekistan, physical education has long been regarded as the main means of strengthening health. Mahmud Koshgari's work "Devonu Lugotit Turk" contains information about more than 100 folk games. "Alpomish" Uzbek folk heroic epic, "Farkhod va Shirin" by Alisher Navoi, "Badoye ul-vaqaye" ("Rare events" by Zayniddin Vasifi), "Boburnoma" by Babur, etc. examples are told.

By the years of independence in Uzbekistan, physical education and sports have risen to the level of state policy.

Wide-ranging system of physical education: family-preschool period (from infancy to kindergarten age), school age, secondary special and higher education period, and adult (male and female) physical education. In Uzbekistan, physical education in secondary schools is considered a pedagogical process and is carried out through physical education classes and training in sports sections. 2 hours a week physical education classes have been introduced in grades 1-9 according to the "State Education Standard of Physical Education for General Secondary Schools". Special tests were developed in 1999 in order to popularize physical education among students and improve their health. "Alpomish" and "Barchinoy" badges of 3 levels were established for those who successfully passed these tests.

General characteristics of physical education tools. During the technological development of the 20th century, physical education and sports are given a big place. Especially in recent years (January 17, 1996). The decree of the President of Uzbekistan on the development of the sport of "football" pleases everyone. Human health has become inseparable from the development of physical education and sports. Because, in the era of technical development, humanity is freed from physical labor and suffers from the most dangerous disease, "Hypodynamia", i.e. inactivity. This leads to the most dangerous cardiovascular disease of the 20th century. Therefore, especially in recent years in our beloved independent republic, the law on "Physical education and sports" and the decree "For a healthy generation" issued by the leaders of our country are important for the spiritual and physical development of children, their healthy, hardworking, happy life. shows cooperation on So, what kind of physical education tools can we use for the physical, all-round harmonious development of the population, especially children.

It is known that physical education has existed since ancient times and developed with human life. A person has gradually chosen the tools for physical education and created the tools of physical education in his life. Physical development of a person is also affected by various activities (work, painting, dressing, etc.), unconditional reflex, massage, etc. They are used in order to strengthen health, develop the organism in all aspects and hormonally, increase the movement, skills and abilities necessary for life, to raise the level of physical improvement to a higher level. However, only if all the means of physical education are used as a whole, it is possible to fully respond to the above-mentioned tasks, because each means has a different effect on the body. These tools are also widely used for treatment and prevention purposes.

Classification is the division of physical exercises into groups and subgroups according to certain characteristics. Different physical exercises have many similar characteristics. It is important to identify the main character that allows you to group exercises. This sign should be pelogologically significant. Classifications made

according to different signs help to get acquainted with many practical physical exercises, to choose the necessary ones according to the tasks, and to quickly find the description of the necessary exercises in textbooks and manuals. In particular, general classifications are based on the historically formed system and methods of physical education: gymnastics, games, sports, tourism. Each of these groups has its own importance and they are divided into smaller classification groups. Gymnastics plays an important role in the system of physical education. It is divided into types of rehabilitation or general development (basic, hygienic, athletic) gymnastics, sports-acrobatics, professional, sports gymnastics, artistic gymnastics (and practical), professional-practical, military-practical, sports-practical, developmental gymnastics, therapeutic gymnastics. Gymnastics has the following specific features: different parts of the body, certain joints, and different aspects of their activity and condition (muscle relaxation, stretching, etc.) use of sports facilities: conducting exercises to music: variety of exercises. These features of gymnastics allow it to be used in exercises with people of all ages, health, and physical fitness to perform various tasks.

Action games. It is a complex activity consisting of various emotional movements. This activity is performed in conditions and situations that suddenly change based on established rules. Unlike gymnastics, it is difficult to distribute physical loads during games.

Movement games differ from other physical exercises in terms of organizing and managing the activities of the participants. During the game, there is a need to act in situations that change suddenly and to perform the tasks of movement in a short period of time, showing physical qualities such as quickness and agility. It strengthens movement skills. During the game, children's activities are organized on the basis of imaginative plots or game tasks, and this creates positive emotions for children to perform physical exercises enthusiastically and for a long time. This, in turn, strengthens their effect on the body, helps to develop endurance.

So, The modern broad concept of "physical education" means an organic component of general education - an educational, pedagogical process aimed at mastering the personal values of physical culture by an individual. In other words, the purpose of physical education is the formation of a person's physical culture, that is, the aspect of human general culture that helps to realize biological and spiritual potential. Physical education, whether we realize it or not, begins in the first days after birth. The terms "Physical education" should be distinguished from vocational training in special educational institutions and "physical education" in its original (according to P.F. Lesgaft) meaning of physical education. In English, the term "physical education" can be used in both senses. It should also be remembered that the English term "en: physical culture" is not used abroad in the sense of our broad understanding of "physical culture". There, depending on the specific direction of physical activity, the words "physical education", "uz: physical education", "en: fitness", etc. are used. Physical education is combined with mental, moral, aesthetic and labor education. In addition, these aspects of the general educational process are manifested to a large extent in the process of physical education organized accordingly.

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